

DataverseNO Organizational Agreement

Organizational Period 2024-2028

*This is an English translation of DataverseNO-forvaltningsavtale
(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10464799>).*

Only the original DataverseNO-forvaltningsavtale is legally binding.

Version log

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1. About this document

DataverseNO has been developed and operated by UiT The Arctic University of Norway (UiT) since 2017. The service was established as a further development of UiT's institutional repository for research data on requests from other Higher Education institutions. Since 2017, the repository has grown continuously and includes 14 partner institutions as of December 2023. DataverseNO has so far been based on a rather informal collaboration between research institutions in Norway. Institutional membership in DataverseNO has been regulated through a common set of policies and guidelines and a partnership agreement between each partner and UiT. The board has consisted of representatives from UiT, and an active user forum has been established where curators exchange experiences and get help and guidance.

Following up on feedback during our CoreTrustSeal certification, it became clear that there is a need to establish a more formalized and robust organizational model that ensures better endorsement, the necessary expertise, and sufficient and long-term funding for the repository.

This document describes the DataverseNO Organizational Agreement that all the institutions using DataverseNO must comply with throughout the applicable Organizational Period.

1.1 Purpose

The DataverseNO Organizational Agreement shall ensure efficient, harmonized, and robust organization of DataverseNO for all institutions that partner with DataverseNO. Organization here means management, operation, and development, and if necessary, discontinuing the service. The agreement describes how DataverseNO is to be organized and covers responsibilities and roles (chapter 2), competency (chapter 3) and funding (chapter 4).

1.2. Guiding principles

The organization of DataverseNO shall, to the greatest extent possible, endorse the principles of good management of research infrastructure as set out in the TRUST Principles for digital repositories (Lin et al. 2020) and the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (Bilder et al. 2020). Overall, there are three guiding principles that shall apply to all aspects of the organization of DataverseNO:

- Guiding principle 1: The organization of DataverseNO must be in line with the requirements of the CoreTrustSeal certification.
- Guiding principle 2: The individual units that are part of the organization of DataverseNO shall have the necessary expertise to ensure the sustainable and long-term organization of DataverseNO according to guiding principle 1. This is described in more detail in chapter 3.
- Guiding principle 3: Sufficient funding shall be provided at any time for the reliable and long-term organization of DataverseNO according to guiding principle 1. This is described in more detail in chapter 4.

1.3 Update

This DataverseNO Organizational Agreement will be reviewed and, if necessary, updated at the latest by the end of the current Organizational Period and otherwise if necessary. Each update must be approved by the Steering Group (see sub-section 2.2) and communicated to the Partner Institutions. The Steering Group is responsible for the document.

2. Responsibilities and roles

Figure 1 gives a schematic overview of the DataverseNO organizational model. The responsibilities and roles of each individual unit are described below the figure.

Figure 1 Schematic overview of the DataverseNO organizational model

2.1 Organizational Documents

The organization of DataverseNO is regulated through these Organizational Documents:

1. DataverseNO Organizational Agreement (= this document)
2. Agreement on Use of DataverseNO (including Data Processor Agreement)
3. DataverseNO Policy Framework
 - a. Access and Use Policy
 - b. Accession Policy
 - c. Deposit Agreement
 - d. Preservation Policy
4. DataverseNO Guidelines
 - a. DataverseNO Guidelines for Repository Management
 - b. DataverseNO Guidelines for Collection Management
 - c. DataverseNO Curation Guidelines
 - d. DataverseNO Deposit Guidelines

The Steering Group is responsible for documents 1, 2 and 3. The Repository Management is responsible for document 4.

2.2 Steering Group

The Steering Group has the overall responsibility for DataverseNO being organized in line with the Organizational Documents (see chapter 2.1).

The starting point for representation in the DataverseNO Steering Group are the three main sectors conducting research in Norway: the HE sector, the Institutes sector, and the Health sector. Within the HE sector, the BOTT universities play a major role in the organization of DataverseNO. Together, these four institutional groups form the starting point for representation in the Steering Group of DataverseNO:

- **BOTT:** The four universities UiB, UiO, NTNU, and UiT (cf. the [BOTT collaboration](#)).
- **HE sector:** Universities (except BOTT), specialised universities, university colleges/universities of applied sciences and university colleges with accredited study programs. See the [overview provided by NOKUT](#).
- **Institutes sector:** Research institutes that are not part of a university or university college. See the sections *Organisations covered by the Government's Strategy for Integrated Institute Policy [...]* and *Other entities in the public sector that are required to conduct research [...]* on the [overview of approved research organization by the Research Council of Norway](#).
- **Health sector:** Health enterprises/hospitals with statutory tasks in research and development and private, non-profit hospitals that are included in the Ministry of Health and Care Services' measurement system for research. See the applicable section on the [overview of approved research organization by the Research Council of Norway](#).

The Steering Group consists of representatives from DataverseNO Partner Institutions in the following way:

- 1 representative from each BOTT institution that is a partner of DataverseNO
- 1 representative from each research sector (HE sector excluding BOTT, Institutes sector, Health sector) that has at least 5 DataverseNO Partner Institutions. Within each sector, representation is rotated between the Partner Institutions, one term of office at a time, in chronological order by the start time of membership in DataverseNO.

The representatives are appointed by the Partner Institutions. It is desirable that the representatives are from the library, research or IT management at the Partner Institutions.

The term of office for the Steering Group is 4 years.

The steering group meets at least twice a year and otherwise as needed.

The Steering Group relates mainly to the Repository Management.

2.3 Repository Management

The Repository Management has the operational responsibility for the DataverseNO repository being organized in line with the Organizational Documents. This responsibility has been assigned to the University Library at UiT.

The Repository Management tasks are taken care of by the DataverseNO service team, which consists of employees at the University Library (UB) and the IT department (ITA) at UiT, and which has its own mandate including responsibilities and roles. The DataverseNO service team ensures the day-to-day operation, maintenance, upgrading and development of DataverseNO, including design and updating of the DataverseNO Organizational Documents, communication with the Steering Group, communication with and training of the Collection Management, organization of the Curation Network, configuration of the repository, creation of institutional collections and sub-collections, user administration, implementation of new functionality and new procedures, planning and coordination of long-term preservation, coordination of minor change requests and prioritization between these, and certification of DataverseNO. The team is also responsible for the management of the top-level collection in DataverseNO, and for contact with suppliers and the international developer and user community of Dataverse and integrated tools and services.

The Repository Management manages and is a discussion partner with the Prioritization Committee dealing with changes in direction, other major changes, and prioritization between these. The

Repository Management raises recommendations from the Prioritization Committee to the Steering Group.

2.4 Collection Management

Each Partner Institution is responsible for their institutional collection being managed in line with the DataverseNO Organizational Documents. This includes data curation, user administration, training of and communication with data curators, communication with the Repository Management, communication with management and the Designated Community at the Partner Institution, and representation of the Partner Institution in the Curation Network. Each Partner Institution has at least one collection manager who takes care of these tasks. As a rule, several curators are involved in the Collection Management.

The Collection Management is an advisor and discussion partner with the Repository Management when it comes to changes and requests for changes.

2.5 Curation Network

Data curation is carried out by curators at the Partner Institutions. Data from non-partner institutions are deposited in the top-level collection and curated by curators at UiT. Data curators are employed at the Partner Institutions. Before publication in DataverseNO, curators ensure that each dataset in the institutional collection is in line with the Organizational Documents and in line with best-practice recommendations and needs from the Designated Community. The curators communicate with the Designated Community represented in the various collections. This happens during curation, but also through other channels and forums.

Curators also communicate with their collection managers and with curators of other collections in DataverseNO through the Curation Network. This network of DataverseNO curators covers the various aspects of data curation, including metadata, file organization and formats, rights and licensing, as well as data privacy and research ethics. In addition to promoting the exchange of knowledge and experience, the Curation Network contributes to ensuring that curation practices are in accordance with the Organizational Documents and aligned across institutional collections.

The Curation Network is an advisor and discussion partner with the Repository Management when it comes to changes and requests for changes.

The Curation Network meets twice a year or when necessary to update on activities in the institutional collections and to discuss relevant topics together with the Repository Management.

In addition, curators across partner institutions meet once a month or as needed to discuss current issues related to the curation of datasets in DataverseNO.

2.6 Designated Community

As DataverseNO offers open and free access to its collections, the Designated Community of the repository consist of both those who contribute data and those who reuse data. The data users are primarily researchers and research institutions, but also other stakeholders in society who depend on access to knowledge, e.g. journalists, teachers, economy as well as the larger society. Communication between data users and the repository takes place primarily through the contact person defined for each dataset, and through the contact point for each individual collection.

In a narrower sense, we can describe the Designated Community of DataverseNO as those groups who, in addition to being data users, also contribute data to the repository, i.e. primarily researchers from Norwegian research institutions who are partners of DataverseNO.

In the day-to-day work, the needs of the Designated Community of the repository are taken care of by the curators. The curators for the institutional collections work at the same institution as the Designated Community of the collection, and many of them communicate closely with the Designated Community also on other issues of research support, e.g. Data Management Plans, Open Access publishing, project applications and literature reviews and searches.

2.7 Partner Institutions

Norwegian research organizations can enter into an agreement to use DataverseNO as a repository for open research data against a start-up fee and an annual service fee. Such an agreement is binding throughout the current Organizational Period. Each Partner Institution gets its own institutional collection in the repository and is responsible for this collection being managed in line with the Organizational Documents, and for user support at its own institution.

Each Partner Institution is responsible for ensuring that the Collection Management at the institution has the necessary resources and expertise to be able to manage the collection and otherwise contribute to the management of DataverseNO in line with the Organizational Documents, and as specified in the chapters on competency and funding below.

When, after the end of the current management period, a Partner Institution no longer wishes to be a partner in the DataverseNO consortium, the institution is responsible for ensuring that all the published datasets in their institutional collection will be available in accordance with the requirements of DataCite (currently for at least 10 years after publication). This must be done through full funding of one of these two alternatives:

- a) The published datasets will remain in DataverseNO.
- b) The published datasets are transferred to another reliable repository which can guarantee that they will be available according to the requirements from DataCite.

2.8 Prioritization Committee

The Prioritization Committee is responsible for assessing and prioritizing suggestions regarding major changes and directional choices related to the DataverseNO organisation, before raising these suggestions to the Steering Group. Furthermore, The Prioritization Committee can also raise and forward suggestions to the Steering Group as necessary.

Suggestions to the Prioritization Committee are primarily submitted by the Repository Management, the Collection Managements, and the Curation Network.

The Prioritization Committee is composed of the following:

- DataverseNO service team leader
- 1 collection manager from each BOTT institution that is a partner of DataverseNO
- 1 collection manager from each research sector (UH sector except BOTT, Institutes sector, Health sector) with at least 5 DataverseNO Partner Institutions. Within each sector, representation is rotated in chronological order according to the start time of membership in DataverseNO.
- 1 representative from the Designated Community. The representation is rotated between Partner Institutions in chronological order by the start time of membership in DataverseNO. The representative from the Designated Community is recruited by the Collection Management at the Partner Institution at stake.

The term of office for the Prioritizing Committee is 4 years.

The Prioritization Committee meets at least twice a year and otherwise as needed. The meeting time should be coordinated with the time of the Steering Group meeting, so that recommendations from the Prioritization Committee are presented to the Steering Group at least 1 week before the Steering Group is to meet.

The Prioritization Committee is led by the DataverseNO service team leader and relates mainly to the Repository Management.

3. Competency

The individual units that are part of the organization of DataverseNO must have the necessary expertise and skills to ensure reliable and long-term management of DataverseNO in line with the requirements of the CoreTrustSeal certification; cf. guiding principle 2 in chapter 1.2 above.

There are currently no fully-fledged competency specifications that cover the entire spectrum of reliable research data repository management. Until such requirements are in place, the competency requirements applicable to the organization of DataverseNO are based on the more general recommendations in the Competency framework for research data management in university and college libraries (Kvale et al. 2023). Unless otherwise mentioned, the competency types described below are taken from this competency framework, hereinafter abbreviated to the Competency Framework.

3.1 Competency Requirements for the Steering Group

The Steering Group shall primarily have expertise and skills within competency type 1 – Administration in the Competency Framework. It is particularly important that the Steering Group be up to date on the strategic developments in research infrastructure provision nationally and internationally.

3.2 Competency Requirements for the Repository Management

The Repository Management shall primarily have expertise and skills within the competency types 3 – Data management, 4 – Ethics and law, 5 – Technical skills, and 6 – Domain knowledge. When it comes to competency types 3 and 4, the Repository Management shall at least have a level of competency that enables them to guide the Collection Management in these areas.

3.3 Competency Requirements for the Collection Management

The Collection Management (including the curators) shall primarily have expertise and skills within competency types 3 – Data management, 4 – Ethics and law and 6 – Domain knowledge, and Software knowledge within competency type 5 – Technical skills.

When appropriate training curricula in research data curation are in place, the competency requirements will be formalized as part of this Organizational Agreement.

4. Funding

Sufficient funding shall be provided at any time for the reliable and long-term organization of DataverseNO in line with the requirements of the CoreTrustSeal certification; cf. guiding principle 3 in chapter 1.2 above. In line with the [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure](#) (Bilder et al. 2020), such funding shall not only cover operational expenses, but also make it possible to adapt the service to new requirements and challenges and create room for strategic development.

4.1 Costs

The funding model of DataverseNO has two main cost elements:

- a) The Partner Institutions shall ensure that they have allocated enough resources to ensure that the Collection Management is aligned with the Organizational Documents. The funding of cost element (a) is something that each Partner Institution provides internally.
- b) The start-up fee and the annual fee that Partner Institutions pay for using DataverseNO shall cover the costs of the Repository Management and, in addition, be used to fund major changes as proposed by the Prioritization Committee.

The costs of the Repository Management are adjusted every year for increases in prices and salaries and specified in an annually updated overview which shall be approved by the Steering Group.

4.2 Pricing Model

In 2023, the annual fees from the Partner Institutions cover approx. 37% of the annual costs UiT has for the operation and development of DataverseNO. In 2024, the coverage rate will be increased to 45%, and then by 5 percentage points each year until the coverage rate is 80% in 2031.

The annual fee per Partner Institution consists of three parts, which are calculated as follows:

- 1) A fixed part which constitutes 70% of the annual fee divided by the number of Partner Institutions as of December 31 in the previous year.
- 2) A variable part which constitutes 15% of the annual fee, and which is based on the number of full-time equivalents (FTEs) in scientific positions at the Partner Institution as of December 31 in the previous year. These figures are based on information from [Database for statistikk om høgare utdanning \(DBH\)](#) and include the following job categories: Undervisnings- og forskarstillingar (UN1), Utdannings- og rekrutteringsstillingar (UN2), Fagleg-administrative leiarstillingar (UN3), Andre undervisnings-, forskings- og formidlingsstillingar (UN4). For Partner Institutions that are not covered by DBH, the numbers are based on information from the Partner Institution or, if such information is not available, on numbers that are freely available on the website of the Partner Institution.
- 3) A variable part which makes up 15% of the annual fee, and which is based on use of the repository measured in numbers of published datasets in the previous year.

In the year they become a member of DataverseNO, new Partner Institutions pay the same amount as existing Partner Institutions pay for the fixed part of the annual fee, but only for each month started in the year they become a member. In addition, new Partner Institutions pay a one-off start-up fee.

Price adjustments that deviate from the price model above must be approved by the Steering Group and notified to the Partner Institutions at least 3 months before invoicing.

4.3 Commitment

The Partner Institutions commit themselves with joint liability to stable funding of DataverseNO throughout the current Organizational Period. This commitment comes in addition to the responsibility

each Partner Institution has if they no longer wish to be partners of the DataverseNO consortium; see chapter 2.7 Partner Institutions.

References

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